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Annotation: *The article deals with the linguistic research of Uzbek construction terms and the history of the emergence of an explanatory dictionary of Uzbek architectural-construction terms and the theoretical issues of its creation. Methodological conclusions are given about the tasks, problems and their solutions, the relevance of creating a dictionary of construction-architecture terms. Focusing on the description of the works carried out in Uzbek and Russian linguistics in this field, the scope of these works is evaluated.*

Keywords: *term, terminology, field terminology, construction field, architecture, lexicography, dictionary, methodology.*

Introduction: The development of the current Uzbek language is greatly influenced by extralinguistic factors - changes in production, science and culture typical of the development after the scientific and technical revolution. A lot of terms related to modern science, technology and architecture-construction are entering the national language. Reworking these terms and adopting them into the Uzbek literary language is one of the urgent issues facing linguistics today.

"Terminology is considered an important link of special lexicography, develops and synthesizes scientific terms. It is the most mobile part of the lexical layer of the language and is considered an important resource for enriching the vocabulary of the language." The need for a stable terminological base and the desire to consciously manage the processes of terminology are becoming more relevant in today's information technology era. From this point of view, the organization and standardization of information obtained in the field of terminology is of particular importance.

In linguistics, the term problem has been discussed for several years. Despite the different opinions on the interpretation of the essence of the term, the understanding of the term as a nominative unit denoting a scientific and technical concept is common to all researchers.

There is no need to mention all the definitions of the term that exist in terminological studies. But let's follow the conceptual thoughts in this regard. D. S. Lotte, one of the founders of the Russian School of Terminology, says, "The main feature of the term is its connection with the scientific and technical concept." In the works of V. P. Danilenko, T. L. Kandelaki, it is noted that "the main sign of a term is the presence of a concrete definition in it."

Based on the complex nature of terms and terminology, we can say that until now (based on the achievements of linguistics, dialectical logic and other disciplines) linguists have been trying to more fully study the issue of scientific and technical terms, their specific semantic character, and the issue of coherence between scientific and technical concepts, terms and definitions.

As a result of the research conducted in this regard, Russian scientist M. A. Marusenko revealed the essence of the concept of the term in a new interpretation: "The concept of a scientific and technical term belongs to the lexicon of the scientific language, it is part of the nominative group (noun or meaningful phrase) related to a certain scientific and technical concept and acquires a special meaning only in the speech of representatives of this scientific

and technical field. Everyday words used in the national language can absorb unlimited connotative content and are a means of communication that is understandable to all speakers of this language; the term is used in the process of describing scientific reality, and the word reflects everyday understanding; the term, as a rule, does not depend on the context, and the meaning of the word emerges in a certain context; terms are classified in a clear order (in terminology) in accordance with the system of scientific concepts, while words do not have such clear systematization; the term does not have emotionality, and the meaning of the word is related to emotions; a term requires a definition that ensures its precise relationship with a certain scientific concept, and a word is polysemy, relying on no clear rules for the transfer of meaning."

If earlier the terminology was important only for the formal aspect of the language, now no one doubts its content-functional importance. This, in turn, causes an increasing number of cases related to terminological problems. Despite the fact that N. Hotamov, B. Sarimsakov, R. Yarkulov, M. Barakayev, S. Bulatov, M. Ashirova, N. Ibodov, A. A'zamov, F. Shvets, I. Sharifboyev, O. Salimov, H. Rasulov, P. Olimkhojaye, F. Is'hakov, A. Kasimov, M. Nabiye, M. Abdullayeva, R. Bekjonov, Sh. Kamolkhojaye and other Uzbek scientists have conducted extensive research on the terms of various fields, the need to analyze the terminology of a number of fields has not abated at all.

In this article, we will talk about the linguistic features of terms related to the construction industry in the Uzbek language. Construction terminology in the Uzbek language includes many terminological units. In them, the conceptual system of the construction industry, one of the industries that occupies an important place in the development of our country, is expressed.

With the acceleration of scientific and technical progress, the construction industry also began to develop rapidly. A plan of complex construction measures has been developed. These scientific and technical programs envisage the development of advanced technologies and methods for the creation of effective construction materials, products and structures, machines and equipment, and their large-scale use. Several government decisions have focused on construction issues. In the modern world, the need for new concepts is increasing, there is a need to change the old ones, construction terminology is being actively supplemented with new terms.

Studying construction terminology in the current situation is one of the urgent issues. Because the latest processes of term formation in construction terminology and the complex of new terms have not been sufficiently analyzed, processed and studied within the field of activity by lexicographers.

It is known that the history of the development of architecture and construction spans several centuries. Consequently, construction terminology is a unique lexical system that was formed in the form of the professional vocabulary of the builders of the early stages of the development of society and has been developing for a long time.

In the terminology of modern construction, one can find terms of different nature in terms of time, sources of formation and principles of nomenclature. This shows that there is a theoretical and practical need to study this field on a broad historical basis, to determine the features of its formation and structure. Many building terms are closely related to the rules of general lexicography and are actively used in the common language. That is why scientific research, which allows to determine the live changes observed in construction terminology, has emerged as an urgent and promising task in this field. In this terminology, a comprehensive analysis of historical processes, the current linguistic and extralinguistic situation, as well as the

changes occurring in various aspects of the people's life, makes it possible to determine the main trends in its development.

Linguistic research of field terminology serves to further clarify the position of the terminological dictionary of architecture and construction in the Uzbek language system. In this, we can see the relevance of specific problems of wide and multifaceted learning of special vocabulary.

Although construction terminology is considered an almost unexplored field in Uzbek linguistics, we can see a number of works in this regard in Russian linguistics. In Russian linguistics, since the valuable scientific works of G. O. Vinokur and D. S. Lotte, issues of terminology have always been in the eyes of linguists. Among the conducted scientific works, there are many works where the object of research is construction terms. Arkadyeva, V. A. Egorov, N. I. Shashkina carried out comprehensive scientific research on the lexical and semantic features of the terms used in the construction system, R. R. Masharipov on the description of basic terms, and S. V. Grinev on the comparative analysis of the English and Russian construction terminology in construction and architecture through the terms used in the Canadian and Russian construction industry.

In Uzbekistan, the book "Russian-Uzbek annotated dictionary of construction materials" by T. A. Otagoziyev, R. O. Mirzayev, the textbook "Glossary of construction machinery" by R. O'. Shukurov, K. Kh. Omonov, M. R. Tajikhojayeva, the methodical manual "Dictionary of English-Russian-Uzbek Terms for Architecture-Construction Specialists" by M. B. Allanyazov were published and it has its importance among the works in this field. Also, M. A. Kuchiboev's research in this direction is noteworthy.

In our opinion, a comprehensive study of the construction terminology of the Uzbek language from the point of view of its historical evolution and current state is very relevant at the moment. In the literature created until now, the question of classification of construction terms according to the field of application has not attracted the attention of researchers, but in specialized literature, valuable ideas about the uniqueness of terms and terminology in general have been mentioned.

In turn, in the process of researching and classifying construction terminology in the Uzbek language, we should pay attention to the following important aspects:

- 1) study the history of formation of construction terminology, determine the sources and methods of formation of construction terms;
- 2) to determine the main structural-semantic types of terms in construction terminology, language tools expressing construction concepts;
- 3) to determine the functional characteristics of construction terminology;
- 4) analysis of the influence of modern requirements during the formation of terms in construction terminology;
- 5) to determine the main trends in the development of construction terminology nomination tools.

The task of researching the study of construction terms based on the process of historical development required us to refer to special literature related to construction from the beginning of the 18th century to the present day. In this case, terms are selected from construction manuals and a special file is created. During this research, the first chronological source can be used as the first chronological source of Yakov Barotsy Devignol's Russian book "Five Important Rules of Architecture" published in 1709. Also, Russian translations and original works on construction, as well as materials from special magazines, serve as an important source for us.

In the selection and analysis of the material (especially in the diachronic aspect), we can rely on the conclusions and observations of historians and archaeologists, in particular, scientists such as I. Y. Zabelin, V. V. Danilevsky. Because, as F.P. Sorokoletov wrote, "it is impossible to understand and explain the vocabulary system, its laws and limits without taking into account the real historical reality that a particular society has experienced." In addition, the index of terms and their usage compiled on the basis of the materials of Soviet newspapers and magazines of 1982-1983 serves as a basis for studying the living processes and current trends of construction terminology development.

The methodological basis of the study of construction terminology is based on the rules of the theory of modern thinking about the existence of a dialectical relationship between reality, thought and language. In this research, we can use the method of linguistic description as the main method. Terminology analysis is carried out in a synchro-diachronic aspect. We can also use the method of mutual comparison of chronological data in a certain sequence. At the same time, a number of other complex methods are used in this field, because the interaction of formal and semantic approaches plays an important role in the analysis of real material. According to the formal approach, the terms are divided into structural types, while the semantic approach allows to determine the methods of forming terms, such as the semantic revision of various word groups in the general literary language.

In the study of construction terminology, the issue of terminology is fundamentally important. Russian linguists made a great contribution to the study of terminology, solving its main issues (the place of terminology in the lexical system of the Russian language, the essence of the term as a linguistic unit). However, many issues in this field are still insufficiently studied and controversial. After all, "in the creation of terms and their definition, two points of view related to the development of the system of concepts of a particular science or field emerge: structural-linguistic and conceptual-semantic."

Conclusion: *We can say that the terms related to the field of architecture and construction in the lexicon of the Uzbek language, which is rapidly developing, have not been sufficiently studied in terms of form and content. This is related to existing conceptual problems in the field of terminology. In the 21st century, the creation of scientific and technical literature in the Uzbek language will remain a difficult issue as long as the standards of the literary language and the lexicon of modern fields and trends in the daily life of the people are not mutually coordinated.*

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